

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AWUKU-ANNIE****FIRST NAME: AUGUSTINE****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Basics of essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-14)
2. Correct application of punctuations (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
3. Differences between American and British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Importance of style guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-43)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2024, 44-51)
7. Referencing (EUCLID 2024, 52-57)

THE FUNDAMENTALS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Relevant knowledge complemented by refined skill sets is indispensable in any successful endeavour. In my life journey, I have sought to imbibe these rich attributes and make them central in my professional and private dealings. My career in the military further projected this drive. Typical of most commissioned officers, I have had a rare opportunity to participate in numerous specialized training and career courses in some renowned institutions worldwide.

By the time I became a major in the army, I had acquired a double master's degree with a third in the offing. I have not achieved my childhood dreams of getting a doctorate, yet I faced a dilemma. I felt overly drained and mentally exhausted to engage in further academic pursuits. However, the frequent nudge to give it a try never ceased.

Finally, I discovered Euclid University on the internet whilst frantically looking for a credible university online where I could comfortably pursue a self-paced but engaging doctorate. The dual intention is to fulfil my awaited childhood dream and become an expert

in a field with the requisite know-how to contribute towards academia and the development of society. I was admitted to the university in November 2023 but started the programme in March 2024.

I found the reference material for the first period of the first course, ACA 401D, very insightful, engaging, and revealing. I discovered that there are many grounds that I need to cover regarding academic writing. In the ensuing paragraphs, I have outlined lessons learned from the study material, notably fundamentals of essay writing, correct application of punctuation, and differences between American and British English. In addition, I will present the importance of style guides, plagiarism, formatting, and referencing.

2) BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

Academic writing, a form of essay, is a veritable means of presenting and preserving information, such as empirical data and research findings, in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals. Academic writings share common approaches, referencing previous findings and answering relevant hypotheses and research questions. The writings also employ formats applicable to the particular publication.

During my reading, I learned that producing a remarkable article demands a rigorous writing process, which must commence early. Generally, it is appropriate to understand the task based on an analysis that also poses related questions. Afterward, the author can develop an initial plan to guide the writing process. Cognizant of existing literature, it is ingenious to interact with the relevant literature at this time, drawing from what is known and actively considering additional information necessary to proffer validated answers to the questions.

I observed that writing involves producing a first draft, redrafting, and editing the text, which comprises an introduction, a body, and a conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 10). Being creative offers ideas that culminate into essays that are engaging and very exciting to read. Overall, it is imperative to reference and present dissenting views. I need to avoid plagiarism while observing the guidelines provided and meeting the deadline.

3) CORRECT APPLICATION OF PUNCTUATION

Punctuations aid a reader in navigating a text in a way that road signs aid drivers and pedestrians in navigating a road. My reading reinforced the usage of basic punctuation, notably commas, full stops, colon and semicolons, brackets, and apostrophes. Beyond that, I discovered varied usage of the other punctuations, which I have yet to consider and use. I noticed that bullet points are not punctuated except if the points form part of a preceding text, then a full stop is added to the end of the last point (EUCLID 2024, 18).

4) DIFFERENCES BETWEEN AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

The British bequeathed the British English to my country and many others they colonized. Globally, American English has recently taken preeminence, including in the British colonies. The study material substantiated the American English dominance. Beyond the variation in spelling, I noticed that some words in one version have different or additional meanings in the other (EUCLID 2024, 26). For example, cereal in British English may refer to maize in American English. I observed differences in the usage of significant collective nouns and pluralized adjectives. An outstanding realization is the influence of culture on how the language is spoken and written in America and Britain. EUCLID recommends using American English and the Chicago Rules (Turabian) writing style (EUCLID 2024, 41).

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism-failure or inappropriate citation of sourced information is unacceptable in academic writing. In addition, outsourcing academic assignments to a third party is tantamount to plagiarism. To substantiate my writing, I must appropriately consult and quote or paraphrase existing information. After that, citing the source using the acceptable referencing style is incumbent.

6) IMPORTANCE OF STYLE GUIDE

A style guide promotes consistency in writing and affords coherence in publications. The elements of the style guide include preferred sentence length, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, and structure (EUCLID 2024, 41). The style guide has benefits for publishers and writers alike. It allows publishers to call for papers from several authors for a particular publication, knowing that variation may be minimal. Writers spend less time editing essays when a specific style guides the writing.

7) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE

The Chicago Manual Style provides a guide for writing my responses and papers. The manual offers directions on several writing details, including abbreviations, capitalizations, compound words, italics and quotation marks, numbers, quotations, and page formats. I am to limit the number of abbreviations used in a particular document. Professor Cleenewerck's video on how to use the style in the ECULID template is apt (Cleenewerck 2016). I appreciated the simplicity and direct approach. The presentation will influence my first and subsequent papers.

8) REFERENCING

Referencing is an aid to avoiding plagiarism. The referencing components are in-text citations, either footnotes or endnotes and a list of works cited. I noted that direct quotations of less than four lines take quotation marks, while long quotations beyond that are indented (EUCLID 2024, 35). I would have to use the Quote Style to get the indent sorted in the EUCLID template. However, it is vital to sparingly use quotations as overuse contests the authenticity and ownership of the research. On the contrary, paraphrasing is a viable resort that allows me to use my own words to explain a borrowed idea, and it is safe to cite something other than standard knowledge information.

9) CONCLUSION

I am excited that my journey towards becoming an expert in a field and achieving my childhood dream has finally commenced with pursuing a doctorate at EUCLID University. Studying the reference document for the first period of the first course, ACA-401D has been insightful and revealing.

The study exposed me to new insights into English that I have yet to explore and utilize in my writing. The fundamentals of essay writing, avoiding plagiarism, using the Chicago Manual Style, applying punctuation, and referencing comprise some of the new insights that I have noted.

Overall, the first period revealed the need to adjust my routines to accommodate this new journey to acquire knowledge. I look forward to taking the subsequent periods and courses.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, dir. 2016. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo.

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